

Inclusive Education Environment As Moderator on Faculty Support and Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers

Rikka Joy A. Sarcauga

Abstract. The present study aimed to assess whether the inclusive education environment moderates the relationship between faculty support and teachers' pedagogical accomplishment. The study involved 178 public elementary school teachers from Digos Oriental District, Digos City, selected using stratified random sampling. A non-experimental quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlational approach was utilized. Data collected were analyzed using statistical tools such as mean, partial correlation, and regression analysis. Descriptive analysis showed that faculty support, pedagogical accomplishment of teachers, and inclusive education environment were rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there was a significant relationship between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City when moderated by an inclusive education environment. Evidently, regression analysis proved that an inclusive education environment has a significant moderating effect on the interaction between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City. The researcher recommended that further studies identify the key variables involved in inclusive education environments, faculty support, and pedagogical accomplishment. The findings are recommended for publication in a reputable research journal for further utilization.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational Management 2. faculty support 3. pedagogical accomplishment of teachers

Date Received: May 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: June 01, 2024 — Date Published: July 5, 2024

1. Introduction

Faculty support, pedagogical accomplishments, and an inclusive education environment are integral to the educational process. They contribute to the quality of education, support teacher development, and create inclusive and equitable learning environments where all students have the opportunity to succeed. Faculty support, including mentoring, coaching, and ongoing professional development, is essential for teachers' continuous professional growth. It helps educators stay up-to-date with best practices, new teaching methods, and changes in curriculum. Also, accomplished teachers can differentiate instruction to meet individual student needs, ensuring that all students can access and understand the curriculum. While, inclusive classrooms reflect the real-world diversity of society. Students learn to interact with peers from various backgrounds and abilities, promoting understanding and tolerance. Jones (2020) characterized the inclusive education environment is an educational approach

that seeks to accommodate all students, including those with diverse backgrounds, abilities, disabilities, and needs, within the regular classroom setting. The goal of inclusive education is to provide equitable access to quality education for all students, regardless of their differences, and to foster a sense of belonging and community within the school. Ezike (2018) found that inclusive education, which welcomes students with diverse backgrounds, abilities, and needs into the regular classroom, presents teachers with unique challenges and opportunities that can profoundly affect their pedagogical practices and professional growth. More so, Monteiro et al. (2021) affirmed that inclusive classrooms often comprise students with a wide range of abilities and learning styles. Kuh et al. (2005) defined faculty support as the assistance, guidance, and resources provided by the academic staff or faculty members to students, colleagues, or other members of the educational community. According to Foster et al. (2019), faculty support not only contributes to the career satisfaction of teachers but also has a direct impact on student outcomes and overall school performance. When teachers are supported, they can perform at their best, positively affecting the learning experiences and achievements of their students. In addition, Johnson and Theaker (2019) conceptualized that a supportive faculty environment fosters a sense of camaraderie among teachers. When educators have a network of colleagues with whom they can share ideas, resources, and experiences, it creates a positive work atmosphere and contributes to job satisfaction. Johnson and Newport (2020) claimed that pedagogical accomplishments create a positive and engaging learning experience for students. When teachers are skilled at delivering content, using interactive methods, and fostering a supportive classroom environment, students are more motivated to learn and participate actively in their education. More so, Fredricks et al. (2012) noted that high-quality teaching captures students' attention and maintains their interest in the subject matter. Engaged students are more likely to be attentive, participate in class discussions, and take ownership of their learning. Likewise, Tomlinson (2014) found that effective teachers are skilled at recognizing and accommodating diverse learning styles and abilities within their classrooms. They can adapt their teaching methods to suit individual needs, ensuring that all students have equal opportunities to succeed. However, Johnson and Newport (2020) highlighted that when teachers' struggle to effectively deliver instruction, it negatively impacts the overall educational experience and can hinder students' academic progress. According to Gershenson et al. (2016), poor pedagogical performance can exacerbate existing achievement gaps among students from different socio-economic backgrounds or diverse learning needs. Thus, students who are already at a disadvantage may fall further behind without effective instruction. In addition to this, Béteille, Kalra, and Shah (2012) reported that schools with consistently poor pedagogical performance may face a decline in reputation and standing within the community, affecting their ability to attract students, funding, and support. While several studies showed that faculty support contributed to the enhancement of teachers' pedagogical accomplishments, Desimone (2009) denoted that faculty support can contribute to a positive teaching experience and enhance the effectiveness of educators. Faculty support may provide access to professional development programs, workshops, and conferences. These opportunities help teachers enhance their instructional skills and stay updated with the latest pedagogical techniques and research. Likewise, Lieberman and Wood (2001) noted that supportive faculty environments foster collaboration among teachers. Collaborative learning communities enable educators to share ideas, resources, and best practices, leading to

improved teaching strategies and student outcomes. While there have been several studies investigating the effect of faculty support on pedagogical accomplishment of teachers, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding the specific mechanisms through which faculty support influences different aspects of pedagogical accomplishment. While existing research has established a positive correlation between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment, there is a need for more in-depth exploration to understand the underlying factors and processes that contribute to this relationship. Thus, it is in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Digos City, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used descriptive correlational design to understand the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers better as determined by the faculty support and inclusive education environment, which is found to be scarce.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Faculty Support*—Faculty support includes the assistance, guidance, and resources provided by academic staff to students and colleagues, significantly impacting their success and well-being (Kuh et al., 2005; Dessler, 2013; Gould-Sandy, 2013). It fosters a positive and inclusive learning environment, encouraging collaboration and open communication (Ellinger, 2016; Tiwari Saxena, 2012; Choudhary Lamba, 2013).

Studies show that faculty support enhances academic excellence by providing mentorship and opportunities for intellectual growth (Dika, 2016; Estep, 2018). It also offers personalized learning experiences, emotional support, and access to professional development, which in turn leads to more engaging and effective teaching methods (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Ingersoll Strong, 2014; Cox et al., 2015; deBoer, 2020).

Furthermore, faculty support helps teachers analyze student performance data and implement personalized learning plans, fostering strong, positive teacher-student relationships that boost motivation and academic performance (Roorda et al., 2014; Foster et al., 2019; Johnson Theaker, 2019; McCarthy et al., 2013; Leithwood et al., 2014).

1.1.2. *Indicators of Faculty Support—Accessibility*: Accessible and approachable teachers significantly improve instruction and student learning by fostering a supportive learning environment and enhancing communication (Kuh et al., 2005; Flaherty, 2019; Frymier Houser, 2012; Pianta et al., 2017; Evertson et al., 2016; Hattie et al., 2015).

Empathy and Understanding: Teachers demonstrating empathy create supportive, inclusive learning environments that foster student engagement and success (Kuh et al., 2005; Hagenauer Volet, 2016; Helliwell et al., 2021; Gay, 2010; Jennings Greenberg, 2014; Elias et al., 1997).

Mentorship: Mentorship provides guidance and support, enhancing teachers' instructional practices and educational outcomes (Kuh et al., 2005; Kim Sax, 2018; Ingersoll Strong, 2014; Chen Wang, 2019; Rasku-Puttonen et al., 2017; Ingersoll Smith, 2004).

Collaboration and Teamwork: Collaborative and cooperative faculty environments improve instruction and student outcomes by sharing ideas, resources, and successful teaching practices (Kuh et al., 2005; Mariskind, 2017; Little, 1990; Johnson Theaker, 2019; Supovitz Turner, 2000; Sawyer, 2012).

1.1.3. *Pedagogical Accomplishment*—Pedagogical accomplishment refers to the effectiveness and quality of instructional practices and their ability to facilitate student learning and achievement. Effective pedagogical practices create positive, engaging learning experiences and accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities (Koopmans et al., 2014; Schaufeli

Salanova, 2011; Klassen et al., 2012; Johnson Newport, 2020; Fredricks et al., 2012; Tomlinson, 2014; Rogers, 2017; Hanushek Rivkin, 2010; Stronge, 2018).

1.1.4. Indicators of Pedagogical Accomplishment—Content Knowledge: Teachers' understanding of their subjects and the curriculum standards allows them to provide accurate, relevant information, effectively convey complex concepts, and boost students' confidence (Stronge, 2018; Song et al., 2018; Gewasari, 2018; Arifin, 2018; Bastian et al., 2019; Hill et al., 2007).

Instructional Strategies: Effective instructional techniques engage students, promote active participation and critical thinking, and accommodate diverse learning styles, contributing to a dynamic learning environment (Stronge, 2018; Warsihna et al., 2019; Rosenshine, 2012; Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Simmonds, 2012; Woolfolk Davis, 2008; Allen et al., 2019).

Assessment and Feedback: Ongoing assessments and timely, constructive feedback help monitor student progress, identify areas for improvement, and inform instructional decisions, fostering academic growth (Stronge, 2018; Hattie Timperley, 2015; O'Donovan, 2017; Gamlem Smith, 2017; Lee Coniam, 2016; Alamis, 2010).

Faculty support significantly enhances teachers' pedagogical accomplishments by providing access to professional development, fostering collaboration, and offering resources and recognition (Desimone, 2009; Lieberman Wood, 2001; Cuban et al., 2010; Niemiec et al., 2018).

1.1.5. Inclusive Education Environment—Inclusive education accommodates students of diverse backgrounds, abilities, and needs within regular classrooms, fostering equitable access to quality education and a sense of belonging (Jones, 2020; Arul Laurence, 2012; Riaz Asad, 2018; Orlu, 2013; Odeh et al., 2015; Shamaki,

2015). Inclusive education environments challenge teachers to become adaptable and proficient in differentiation, enhancing their pedagogical skills (Ezike, 2018; Monteiro et al., 2021; Usman Madudili, 2019). It fosters collaboration, empathy, and professional development, leading to greater faculty support and improved pedagogical practices (Mudassir Norsuhaily, 2015; Gilavand, 2015; Murugan Rajoo, 2013).

1.2. Synthesis—The effect of faculty support on the teaching performance of teachers is a critical factor in shaping the overall quality of education and student outcomes. Research suggests that when teachers receive substantial support from their colleagues, administrators, and educational institutions, their teaching performance improves significantly. One crucial aspect of faculty support is the provision of professional development opportunities. When teachers have access to workshops, conferences, and training programs, they can enhance their instructional skills and stay abreast of innovative teaching strategies (Desimone, 2009). Collaborative learning communities also play a significant role in faculty support. When educators have the chance to engage in collaborative practices, such as sharing ideas and best practices, it positively influences their teaching approaches (Lieberman Wood, 2001). Effective feedback and evaluation mechanisms provided as part of faculty support further contribute to enhancing teaching performance. When teachers receive constructive feedback and evaluation, they can identify areas for improvement and capitalize on their strengths. Access to resources and technology is another essential element of faculty support. When teachers have the necessary teaching materials, resources, and technology tools, they can adopt innovative and engaging instructional approaches that positively impact student learning. In summary, faculty support significantly influences teaching performance. Access to professional development, collabora-

tive learning, mentoring, feedback, resources, and recognition all contribute to a supportive environment that enhances teachers' abilities to create meaningful learning experiences for their students. By nurturing and empowering teachers, faculty support plays a crucial role in shaping the overall success of the teaching-learning process.

1.3. *Theoretical/Conceptual Framework*—

The current study was anchored on Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura (1986). According to the Social Cognitive Theory, by addressing teachers' self-efficacy, outcome expectations, observational learning experiences, and social support, faculty support can promote positive changes in teachers' instructional practices and lead to improved teaching performance and student learning outcomes. In an inclusive education environment, teachers have the opportunity to observe and learn from each other's inclusive teaching practices. Faculty members who effectively implement inclusive strategies serve as models for their colleagues, demonstrating how to adapt teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of students. Observing successful inclusive practices can inspire other teachers to adopt similar approaches, leading to increased pedagogical accomplishment. In support, Mudassir and Norsuhaily (2015) proposed that inclusive education fosters a collaborative and communicative environment among faculty members. Teachers may need to work closely together to develop and implement inclusive teaching strate-

The measure of faculty support, according to Kuh et al. (2005) are accessibility or the accessibility and approachability of teachers; empathy and understanding or the ability to demonstrate empathy and understanding towards the challenges and needs of students and colleagues; mentorship or the extent of guidance and support given to the less-experienced colleagues or students in their academic or pro-

gies that meet the diverse needs of all students. This collaboration can lead to increased faculty support as educators share resources, ideas, and strategies to enhance pedagogical practices. More so, collaboration among faculty members allows teachers to leverage their collective expertise, experiences, and resources to create inclusive learning environments where every student can thrive. Teachers may engage in collaborative planning sessions, professional learning communities, or interdisciplinary teams to share insights, discuss challenges, and co-create inclusive teaching practices. In addition, Gilavand (2015) intellectualized that in an inclusive education environment, teachers develop a deeper understanding of the diverse needs and backgrounds of their students. This heightened awareness fosters empathy and understanding among faculty members, leading to greater support for each other's pedagogical efforts. This highlights the transformative impact of inclusive education on teacher awareness and empathy within the educational environment. In an inclusive classroom, teachers are confronted with a diverse range of students, each with unique backgrounds, abilities, and learning needs. As shown in Figure 1, the study was consist of three variables. The independent variable is faculty support or the assistance, guidance, and resources provided by the academic staff or faculty members to students, colleagues, or other members of the educational community.

fessional journeys; and collaboration and teamwork or the collaborative and cooperative atmosphere among faculty members, encouraging teamwork and shared responsibilities. The dependent variable was pedagogical accomplishment or the effectiveness and quality of an educator's instructional practices and their ability to facilitate student learning and achievement. The measure of pedagogical accomplishment

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

according to Stronge (2018) content knowledge or the teachers’ understanding of the subjects they teach and their knowledge about the curriculum, standards, and the latest developments in their field of expertise; instructional strategies or the various instructional techniques and methodologies to engage students with diverse learning styles; and assessments and feedbacks or the implementation of ongoing assessments to monitor student progress and identify areas for improvement. The moderating variable was an inclusive education environment or an edu-

cational approach that seeks to accommodate all students, including those with diverse backgrounds, abilities, disabilities, and needs, within the regular classroom setting (Jones, 2020).

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The study’s primary aim was to evaluate the moderating effect of an inclusive education environment on the interaction between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City. Specifically, the study has the following objectives:

- (1) What is the extent of faculty support in terms of:
 - (1) accessibility;
 - (2) empathy and understanding;
 - (3) mentorship; and
 - (4) collaboration and teamwork?
- (2) What is the extent of pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) content knowledge;
 - (2) instructional strategies; and
 - (3) assessment and feedbacks?
- (3) What is the extent of the inclusive education environment in Digos Oriental, Digos City?
- (4) Is there a significant relationship between faculty support and the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental, Digos City, when moderated by an inclusive education environment?
- (5) Does the inclusive education environment moderate the interaction between faculty support and the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental, Digos City?

1.5. *Hypothesis*—The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental, Digos City when moderated by an inclusive education environment. H02: An inclusive education environment does not moderate the interaction between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental, Digos City. The study would benefit the following organizations and individuals: Department of Education. Department of Education could use the research findings to develop informed education policies that enhance the quality of teacher support and pedagogical practices in inclusive settings. Also, the study can help allocate resources more effectively, ensuring that schools have the necessary support structures and professional development programs in place. Policymakers. Research on the impact of faculty support could provide policymakers with evidence-based insights into the effectiveness of various support mechanisms. This information could guide developing and implementing policies that effectively enhance teaching quality and student learning outcomes. Policymakers could establish accountability measures based on the impact of faculty support on teaching performance. These measures could be more meaningful and aligned with improving instructional practices and student outcomes. School Heads. School heads could use research findings to allocate resources more efficiently, directing support and professional development efforts where they are needed most within the school. Adding more, understanding how faculty support interacts with the inclusive environment could in-

form the design of more targeted and effective professional development programs for teachers. Teachers. Faculty support could directly impact teachers' instructional practices and their ability to engage students effectively. Understanding the effect of different types of support could help identify the most impactful approaches to improving teacher effectiveness. Future researchers. Other researchers could contribute to the body of knowledge on inclusive education, faculty support, and pedagogical accomplishment by exploring the moderating effects in depth, adding to the existing literature. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Faculty Support may be conceptually defined as the assistance, guidance, and resources provided by academic staff or faculty members to students, colleagues, or other members of the educational community. This study describes the independent variable in terms of accessibility, empathy and understanding, mentorship, collaboration, and teamwork. Pedagogical Accomplishments of Teachers were conceptually defined as the effectiveness and quality of an educator's instructional practices and their ability to facilitate student learning and achievement. This refers to the dependent variable of the study, which was described in terms of content knowledge, instructional strategies, and assessment and feedback. Inclusive Education Environment was conceptually defined as an educational approach that seeks to accommodate all students, including those with diverse backgrounds, abilities, disabilities, and needs, within the regular classroom setting. In this study, it was considered the moderating variable, which helps understand when, where, and how the relationship between two other variables changes or varies.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps

involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research technique to collect data on the influence of faculty support, the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers, and the inclusive education environment. According to Bryman and Bell (2015), quantitative research is characterized by its focus on objectively measuring and analyzing numerical data to draw conclusions and make inferences about a specific population or phenomenon. This approach utilizes systematic and structured data collection methods, such as surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis of existing datasets, to gather quantitative and statistically examined numerical data. Quantitative research findings aim to provide a deeper insight into patterns, relationships, and trends within the collected data. Meanwhile, descriptive correlational research, according to Gay, Mills, and Airasian (2019), an approach that involves observing and measuring two or more variables without manipulating them. It aims to describe the relationship or association between variables as they naturally occur. This approach focuses on understanding the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, often using statistical measures such as correlation coefficients. In a descriptive correlational study, researchers collect data on variables of interest and analyze them to identify patterns, trends, or associations. The goal was to better understand how the variables relate to each other in a specific population or context. Specifically, the study investigated the relationships among variables to determine the

moderating effect of an inclusive education environment on the interaction between faculty support and the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers. In this study, the use of hierarchical regression analysis would be appropriate because the researchers can develop more accurate and context-specific predictive models. Instead of assuming a constant relationship between variables, they could account for variations based on the moderating variable's influence.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents in this research were elementary school teachers from Digos Oriental District, located in Digos City. The study utilized a sample size of 178 respondents, selected through stratified random sampling. Stratified random sampling involves dividing the population into smaller groups or strata. This study employed specific inclusion criteria to identify suitable respondents who could provide relevant information to fulfill the study's objectives. The main focus was to select respondents who could contribute information essential for achieving the study's purpose. The inclusion criteria were as follows: teachers with a minimum of two years of teaching experience to ensure they have sufficient experience in the classroom; teachers who have received training or have experience in inclusive education practices to ensure they have knowledge of and experience with inclusive teaching methods; teachers with proficiency in the language of the study's instruments like English or the local language to ensure accurate comprehension and response; and teachers who voluntarily agree to participate in the research and

provide informed consent.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—Three sets of instruments were used in this study. A panel of experts subjected these questionnaires to content validity testing and underwent pilot testing to test their validity and reliability. The experts’ comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires. The first part of the instrument concerned faculty support, which was conceptualized by Kuh et al. (2005). The instrument

consists of four domains, namely accessibility, empathy and understanding, mentorship, and collaboration and teamwork. The reliability of the new scale obtained an overall Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.970. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of faculty support, the researcher used various means, descriptions, and interpretations, as presented below.

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The faculty support is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The faculty support is often-times observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The faculty support is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The faculty support is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The faculty support is never observed.

The second tool is about the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers. This was intellectualized by Stronge (2018). The teacher’s pedagogical accomplishment questionnaire consisted of statements divided into indicators: content knowledge, instructional strategies, and assessment and feedback. The reliability of the new scale obtained an overall Cronbach’s alpha

value of 0.927. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers’ pedagogical accomplishment, the researcher used various means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below.

The third tool is about an inclusive education environment. This was intellectualized by Jones (2020). The reliability of the new scale obtained an overall Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.941. In the manner of answering the question-

naire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers’ pedagogical accomplishment, the researcher used a range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The

researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School; and the ethical clearance certificate from RMC-

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The pedagogical accomplishment of teachers is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The pedagogical accomplishment of teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The pedagogical accomplishment of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The pedagogical accomplishment of teachers is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The pedagogical accomplishment of teachers is never manifested.

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The inclusive education environment is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The inclusive education environment is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The inclusive education environment is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The inclusive education environment is rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The inclusive education environment is never evident.

Research Ethics Committee. The endorsement letter and ethical clearance certificate from Research Ethics Committee were attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the schools' division superintendent, and then to the school principals of the selected public elementary schools in the Digos Oriental District, Digos City. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the approval to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. The researcher conducted the survey simultaneously to administer the questionnaire. The study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analy-

sis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher asked for the permission of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly

informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were given to them for a better understanding of the reason for their participation so that they could choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondent's involvement in the study is voluntary. If they refused to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to survey the factors that hinder/promote the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers concerning faculty support and inclusive education environment and may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The respondents of the study are teachers so they were not considered vulnerable since all of them are in legal age, and, they were not considered highly vulnerable in the psychological aspect. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the data Privacy Act of 2012 wherein the researcher assured that the data cannot be traced back to the respondents which was the real source of information, to protect the identities of the respondents. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the respondents. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, the access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person that could access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed all the survey result to assure that data cannot be traced back to the respondents who were the real source of information. Risk, Benefits and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the

researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study as well as the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. The respondents, without restrictions were able to ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not be subjected to harm in any ways whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire that were used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents of the study. Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect academic information related to the study and they were not asked with personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher made sure that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire online. The respondents were given freedom not to answer questions which made them feel any psychological and emotional distress and they would be free to withdraw as a respondent of the study if they would feel that they cannot discuss the information that being asked from them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the course of the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equal regardless if they would be respondent in the survey. The researcher did not prejudiced in choosing the respondents of the study. Anybody who fitted the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the conduct of the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting as little time as possible to the routine of the respondents. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any type of communication in relation to the research was done with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the respondents, the researcher properly implemented the methods that are dis-

cussed to use in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis was included. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that the responses of the respondents were not influence by any other factor like the conflict of interest. The findings of the study could be accessed by the respondents and stakeholders, and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the study, the Division of Davao del Sur was given a furnished copy of the results of the research so it can be accessed by the respondents and be used for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials which were ample and available in the conduct of the study and was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding properly the ratings of the respondents during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results gathered were proficient and aligned that serves as a primary basis for ad-

equacy. Community Involvement. It was a good practice to have community involvement during every phase of research from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement were accorded with primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the faculty support, pedagogical accomplishments of teachers, and inclusive education environment in Digos Oriental, Digos City. Partial Correlation Analysis. It was used in this study to asses the significant relationship among faculty support, pedagogical accomplishments of teachers, and inclusive education environment in Digos Oriental, Digos City. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample it is usually denoted by r . Hierarchical Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the moderating effect of inclusive education environment on the interaction between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishments of teachers in Digos Oriental, Digos City.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It was sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of faculty support, pedagogical accomplishment of teachers, and inclusive education environment in Digos Oriental District, Digos City; the significant relationship between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City when moderated by inclusive education environment; and the moderateing effect of inclusive education environment on the interaction between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City.

3.1. Faculty Support for Teachers—

3.1.1. *Accessibility*—Table 1 indicates that respondents perceived faculty support in terms

of accessibility as extensive, with a category mean of 3.51, suggesting that teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City, are oftentimes ob-

served. This suggests that teachers frequently offer the assistance, direction, and motivation necessary for students to succeed in demanding academic settings. In academic environments, teachers serve as mentors, guides, and sometimes even as role models for students navigating through the complexities of their studies.

This finding aligns with Pianta et al.’s (2017) claim that friendly teachers establish positive bonds with students built on trust and admiration. These bonds foster an environment conducive to learning, as students are more inclined to seek assistance, work together, and feel nurtured in their educational pursuits.

Table 1. Faculty Support in Terms of Accessibility

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Making sure to respond to student emails within twenty four hours.	3.48	Extensive
Being available for our students is part of our responsibility as educators.	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Providing alternative communication channels for the learners.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Believing in fostering a sense of community among students.	3.54	Extensive
Trying to create an inclusive classroom environment where students feel comfortable asking questions during class.	4.12	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.51	Extensive

The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.14 to 4.12. On the one hand, the item “Being available for our students is part of our responsibility as educators” has a mean rating of 3.14, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents. On the other hand, the item “Trying to create an inclusive classroom environment where students feel comfortable asking questions during class” reflects a mean of 4.12, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by faculty support. This shows that when teachers are perceived as approachable, students are more likely to feel comfortable expressing their thoughts, concerns, and questions. This open line of communica-

tion enables teachers to gain insights into their students’ individual needs and challenges. The findings align with Evertson et al.’s (2016) concept that approachable teachers foster effective communication with students. This communication facilitates teachers in comprehending the unique requirements and difficulties of each student, empowering them to customize instruction to address those needs efficiently.

3.1.2. Empathy and Understanding—The findings presented in Table 2 indicate that faculty support in terms of empathy and understanding received an extensive category mean rating of 3.42, suggesting that this type of support is oftentimes observed by teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City.

The result implies that when teachers demonstrate empathy—showing sensitivity to students’ feelings and perspectives—and understanding—recognizing students’ challenges and circumstances—they create an environment conducive to learning and growth. The outcome corroborates Hagenauer and Volet’s (2016) notion that empathy and understanding wield

significant influence, positively affecting instruction and enhancing student learning outcomes. When educators exhibit empathy and understanding, they establish a nurturing and all-encompassing learning atmosphere, fostering student involvement, drive, and academic achievement.

Table 2. Faculty Support in Terms of Empathy and Understanding

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Trying to put myself in my students’ shoes and understand their perspectives.	4.11	Extensive
Believing that being understanding is key to helping students overcome obstacles they might be facing outside the classroom.	3.78	Extensive
Trying to be approachable and approach each student with an open mind.	2.15	Less Extensive
Making an effort to learn about my students’ interests, struggles, and aspirations.	3.89	Extensive
Make it a point to actively listen to my students during one-on-one meetings and in-class discussions.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.42	Extensive

The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.15 to 4.11. The item “Trying to be approachable and approach each student with an open mind” reflects a mean rating of 2.15 described as less extensive and interpreted as item rarely observed. Meanwhile, the item “Trying to put myself in my students’ shoes and understand their perspectives it” shows a rating of 4.11, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed by the teachers. This shows that when teachers exhibit empa-

thy, they convey a genuine concern for their students’ well-being and experiences, fostering a sense of connection and rapport. Similarly, understanding students’ individual challenges and circumstances allows teachers to respond with compassion and support, strengthening the bond between them. This finding aligns with Helliwell et al.’s (2021) suggestion that teachers who demonstrate empathy and understanding develop robust and trustworthy bonds with their students. These relationships serve as the cor-

nerstone for fostering open communication and establishing a supportive environment where students feel comfortable sharing their thoughts, worries, and obstacles.

3.1.3. *Mentorship*—Specifically, faculty support in terms of mentorship acquired a category mean of 3.11, which was described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondent. The result indicates that by recognizing what each teacher excels at, mentors can provide targeted guidance to help them further develop these strengths. Ad-

ditionally, mentors assist teachers in identifying areas for improvement and provide constructive feedback to facilitate growth in those areas. This corroborates the discoveries made by Chen and Wang (2019) indicating that mentorship provides customized professional growth suited to the particular requirements and aspirations of mentees. Through focusing on individual strengths and areas needing improvement, mentors can assist educators in enhancing their instructional abilities and honing their teaching methodologies.

Table 3. Faculty Support in Terms of Mentorship

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Making myself available to my students as a mentor, providing guidance, and helping them set realistic goals.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Striving to create a supportive environment where students feel comfortable approaching me for advice or sharing their concerns.	3.42	Extensive
Sharing my own experiences and challenges to let them know that setbacks are a natural part of the learning process.	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Trying to meet with my mentees regularly, listen to their concerns, and provide guidance to help them navigate challenges effectively.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Setting clear goals with my mentees.	2.46	Less Extensive
Overall Mean	3.11	Moderately Extensive

The table also indicates that the mean ratings of the items vary from 2.46 to 3.42. Notably, the item "Setting clear goals with my mentees" has a mean rating of 2.46, indicating a less extensive rating, suggesting it is rarely observed. Conversely, the item "Striving to create

a supportive environment where students feel comfortable approaching me for advice or sharing their concerns" has a mean rating of 3.42, signifying an extensive rating, interpreted as being frequently observed by teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City. The findings align

with Kim and Sax’s (2018) claim that mentorship provides teachers with the necessary support, guidance, and encouragement to enhance their professional development, ultimately resulting in improved instructional methods and positive student educational results.

3.1.4. *Collaboration and Teamwork*—Results in Table 4 show that faculty support in terms of collaboration and teamwork got a moderately extensive category mean rating of 3.33 and interpreted as sometimes observed. The outcome suggests that a cooperative and collaborative environment that fosters teamwork

and shared duties is sometimes observed. In educational settings where collaboration is encouraged, teachers have the opportunity to work together, share ideas, and support one another in their professional growth. This aligns with Johnson and Theaker’s (2019) notion that collaboration is a support network for novice or less experienced educators. They have the opportunity to seek counsel and input from seasoned peers, aiding in enhancing their teaching abilities and navigating teaching challenges more adeptly.

Table 4. Faculty Support in Terms of Collaboration and Teamwork

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Collaborating with my colleagues to design interdisciplinary projects that engage students from different subjects.	4.06	Extensive
Encouraging group projects and peer learning activities in the classroom.	3.98	Extensive
Collaborating with other teachers on cross-curricular projects and initiatives.	2.16	Less Extensive
Trying to create interdisciplinary projects that make learning more engaging and relevant for the students.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Encouraging a culture of open communication and sharing ideas.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.33	Moderately Extensive

The average rating of the various items varies from 2.16 to 4.06. The item “Collaborating with other teachers on cross-curricular projects and initiatives” reflects a mean rating of 2.16, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item rarely observed. Conversely, the item “Collaborating with my colleagues to design

interdisciplinary projects that engage students from different subjects” shows a rating of 4.06, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed by the teachers. This denotes that collaborative analysis of student data allows teachers to gain valuable insights into student progress and learning outcomes. Through

discussions and data-driven reflections, teachers can identify effective instructional interventions, tailor teaching approaches to individual student needs, and implement targeted support strategies. The findings align with the suggestion put forth by Supovitz and Turner (2000) that collaboration enables teachers to collectively examine student data and make well-informed decisions regarding instruction.

3.1.5. *Shows The Summary of the Faculty Support for Teachers*—Lastly, Table 5 summa-

rizes faculty support for teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City. It shows that the overall mean of faculty support is 3.34, which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. The outcome suggests that the support, guidance, and resources offered by academic staff or faculty members to students, colleagues, or other educational community members are frequently observed in Digos Oriental District, Digos City.

Table 5. Summary of Faculty Support in Digos Oriental District, Digos City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Accessibility	3.51	Extensive
Empathy and Understanding	3.42	Extensive
Mentorship	3.11	Moderately Extensive
Collaboration and Team Work	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.34	Moderately Extensive

This finding aligns with Ellinger’s (2016) notion that faculty support is crucial in fostering a positive and inclusive learning environment. When faculty members are approachable, empathetic, and supportive, students feel at ease seeking assistance and sharing their thoughts, cultivating a collaborative and transparent classroom environment. More so, faculty support in terms of accessibility acquired the highest mean score of 3.51, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while faculty support in terms of mentorship got the lowest mean score of 3.11, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed, by teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City. This emphasizes the significant role of faculty support in promoting academic excellence among students. Faculty members play a crucial role beyond delivering content—they provide valuable feedback, guidance, and mentorship to students. The outcome aligns with Dika’s (2016) suggestion that faculty support contributes to academic

excellence by offering students beneficial feedback, mentorship, and avenues for intellectual development. This fosters students’ aspirations for greater achievement and cultivates a climate of ongoing enhancement.

3.2. *Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers*—

3.2.1. *Content Knowledge*—Table 6 indicates that the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in terms of content knowledge was rated as moderately extensive, with a category mean of 3.27. This suggests that teachers’ pedagogical accomplishments are sometimes manifested. This suggests that teachers successfully communicated intricate ideas in a comprehensible and approachable manner, which is crucial for aiding students in comprehending the material and fostering a profound understanding of the subject. The finding aligns with Song et al.’s (2018) assertion that teachers’ mastery of content is a cornerstone of effective teaching and significantly influences the teaching-learning

dynamic. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.45 to 4.13. The item “Offering extra practice exercises and individualized tutoring to tackle their difficulties” shows a mean rating of 2.45, which is described as less extensive and interpreted as this item rarely observed among teachers. Further, the item “Promoting inquiries and dialogues, cultivating a classroom atmosphere where they feel at ease asking for clarification and expressing their ideas” has a mean rating of 4.13, described as extensive and interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested.

Table 6. Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers in Terms of Content Knowledge

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Explaining complex concepts in a way that is easy for them to grasp.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
Anticipating misconceptions and addressing them proactively, which minimizes confusion and promotes a deeper understanding.	3.42	Extensive
Promoting inquiries and dialogues, cultivating a classroom atmosphere where they feel at ease asking for clarification and expressing their ideas.	4.13	Extensive
Adjusting my lessons based on individual student needs, providing extra support to those who struggle and challenging those who excel.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Offering extra practice exercises and individualized tutoring to tackle their difficulties.	2.45	Less Extensive
Mean	3.27	Moderately Extensive

The result implies that teachers who possess a deep understanding of the content are better equipped to convey complex ideas in a manner that is accessible to students. They have the proficiency to organize information in a logical sequence, present it in a clear and concise manner, and illustrate key concepts with relevant examples. The finding aligns with Arifin’s (2018) assertion that teachers with a profound grasp of the subject matter can articulate information clearly and coherently. They have the ability to elucidate intricate concepts, establish links among various topics, and offer pertinent examples, thereby rendering the content more understandable and captivating for students.

3.2.2. *Instructional Strategies*—This domain in the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in terms of instructional strategies, as shown in Table 7, reflects an extensive category mean of 3.44, which means that it is oftentimes manifested by the teachers. This suggests that educators frequently demonstrate deliberate de-

cisions and techniques in planning, organizing, and delivering instruction to students. By employing deliberate choices and techniques, educators can tailor their instruction to address their students’ specific learning objectives and preferences.

Table 7. Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers in Terms of Instructional Strategies

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Engaging students through discussions, group activities, and hands-on projects.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Prioritizing essential concepts and being creative in integrating active learning activities within the curriculum.	3.45	Extensive
Using various instructional materials and offering choices in assignments.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
Providing additional support for struggling students.	3.98	Extensive
Accommodating different learning styles and abilities to increase students’ participation.	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.44	Extensive

This may involve differentiating instruction to accommodate various learning styles, providing scaffolding for struggling learners, or incorporating technology to enhance engagement and accessibility. The outcome aligns with Warsihna et al.’s (2019) proposition that teachers’ adept instructional methods are crucial in establishing an active and efficient learning atmosphere. These strategies enhance student engagement, motivation, and overall academic achievement, nurturing a passion for learning that transcends traditional classroom boundaries. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.23 to 3.98. The table further reveals that the item “Accommodating different learning styles and abilities to increase students’ participation” has a mean rating of 3.23 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as item sometimes manifested by the teachers. Meanwhile, the item “Providing additional sup-

port for struggling students” has mean rating of 3.98 described as extensive and interpreted as pedagogical accomplishment of teachers is oftentimes manifested. This shows that when teachers utilize techniques that are engaging and compelling, they capture students’ attention and stimulate their curiosity about the subject matter. These strategies encompass a variety of approaches, such as interactive discussions, hands-on activities, multimedia presentations, and real-world applications. The findings support Darling-Hammond et al.’s (2017) assertion that proficient instructional methods effectively captivate students’ focus and sustain their interest in the material. Engaged students are inherently more motivated and inclined to actively participate in the educational journey.

3.2.3. *Assessment and Feedbacks*—This domain, as shown in Table 8, has a category mean of 3.24, described as moderately exten-

sive and interpreted that this domain of pedagogical accomplishments of teachers is sometimes manifested. The outcome suggests that the organized assessment of students' progress and the offering of constructive feedback to aid in their comprehension of strengths and areas needing development occur occasionally in

Digos Oriental District, Digos City. This observation supports Simmonds's (2012) suggestion that employing such methods promotes student engagement, critical analysis, and problem-solving skills. Active participation in learning fosters a more profound grasp of the subject matter, enhancing retention.

Table 8. Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers in Terms of Assessment and Feedback

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Using a variety of formative and summative assessments to gauge my students' understanding of the material.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
When providing feedback, I focus on being constructive and encouraging.	3.62	Extensive
Making sure my feedback is specific to each student's work and learning style.	3.89	Extensive
Offering additional resources if students struggle.	2.16	Less Extensive
Believing in giving students multiple opportunities to demonstrate their understanding of the material.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.24	Moderately Extensive

Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.16 to 3.89. Specifically, the item "Offering additional resources if students struggle" has a mean rating of 2.16, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item rarely manifested by the teachers. The item "Making sure my feedback is specific to each student's work and learning style" reflects a mean rating of 3.89, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested by the teachers. The result emphasizes the importance of employing effective learning strategies to enhance students' memory retention and recall

abilities. Techniques such as spaced repetition involve reviewing information at increasing intervals over time, which strengthens memory consolidation and retention. The finding aligns with Allen et al.'s (2019) claim that utilizing methods such as spaced repetition, mnemonics, and concept mapping can enhance students' capacity to remember and retrieve information.

3.2.4. *Pedagogical Accomplishments of Teachers*—Lastly, as shown in Table 9, is the summary of the pedagogical accomplishments of teachers. As shown in the table, the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers obtained

an overall mean score of 3.32 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City.

Table 9. Summary of Pedagogical Accomplishments of Teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Content Knowledge	3.27	Moderately Extensive
Instructional Strategies	3.44	Extensive
Assessment and Feedback	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.32	Moderately Extensive

The result indicates that the effectiveness and quality of an educator’s instructional practices and their ability to facilitate student learning and achievement are sometimes manifested among teachers. This finding agrees with the view of Schaufeli and Salanova (2011) that pedagogical accomplishment constructs reflect the feelings of energy that lead the teacher to act in an energetic fashion. When teachers feel energized and enthusiastic about their work, they are more likely to exhibit proactive and dynamic behaviors in the classroom. This may include employing innovative teaching methods, fostering interactive learning environments, and actively engaging with students to facilitate their learning. The sense of energy and enthusiasm that teachers bring to their roles can have a significant impact on student motivation, engagement, and academic achievement. Adding more, results in Table 9 show that the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in terms of instructional strategies acquired the highest mean score of 3.44 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. In contrast, the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in terms of assessment and feedback acquired the lowest mean score of 3.24 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the teachers. This shows that effective pedagogical practices prioritize student-centered learning, active participation, and meaningful

interactions. Teachers who employ these practices create learning environments that are conducive to student growth, development, and success. The finding corroborates Johnson and Newport’s (2020) assertion that proficient pedagogical methods foster a favorable and captivating learning atmosphere for students.

3.2.5. *Inclusive Education Environment*—

This domain, as shown in Table 10, has a category mean of 3.27, described as moderately extensive and interpreted that an inclusive education environment is sometimes evident. This means that the educational strategy aiming to include all students, regardless of their diverse backgrounds, abilities, disabilities, and requirements, in the standard classroom environment is occasionally observed. This corresponds with Arul Laurence’s (2012) viewpoint that engaging with students from diverse backgrounds and abilities fosters empathy and understanding among educators. This heightened empathy can lead to more compassionate and student-centered teaching methods, thereby enhancing pedagogical effectiveness. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.46 to 4.13. Specifically, the item “Differentiated instruction to meet the varied learning needs of students in your classroom” has a mean rating of 2.46, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item rarely manifested by the teachers. The item “Necessary accommodations and sup-

port are consistently provided to students with diverse needs in your school” reflects a mean rating of 4.13, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes evident. This

shows that inclusive education aims to create learning environments that accommodate and support every student, fostering a sense of belonging and acceptance.

Table 10. Summary of Inclusive Education Environment in Digos Oriental District, Digos City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Parents actively involved in the planning and implementation of inclusive education programs for their children.	3.11	Moderately Extensive
There are specific strategies in place to address behavior management and emotional support for students with behavioral challenges.	3.42	Extensive
Necessary accommodations and support are consistently provided to students with diverse needs in your school.	4.13	Extensive
The use of segregative practices, such as placing students with disabilities in separate classrooms or schools, is reduced.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Differentiated instruction to meet the varied learning needs of students in your classroom.	2.46	Less Extensive
Overall Mean	3.27	Moderately Extensive

This finding aligns with the proposition put forth by Riaz and Asad (2018) that inclusive education aims to provide every student, regardless of their abilities or differences, with equitable access to high-quality education. Inclusive education promotes fairness in education, thereby mitigating differences in academic achievements.

3.2.6. *Relationship Between Faculty Support and Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City When*

moderated by an Inclusive Education Environment—The results of the analysis of the relationship between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishments of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City, when moderated by an inclusive education environment are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 11 shows that faculty support has a significant positive relationship with

the pedagogical accomplishments of teachers when moderated by an inclusive education environment with a p-value of .000 that is less than a .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .848, p \leq 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the faculty support changes, the pedagogical accomplishments of teachers also significantly change when moderated by an inclusive education environment. More so, the result in the table shows that faculty support in terms of accessibility,

empathy, and understanding significantly correlated with the pedagogical accomplishments of teachers when moderated by an inclusive education environment, as evident by correlation coefficient values of 0.544 and 0.742, respectively. Thus, this led to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between faculty support and the pedagogical accomplishments of teachers when moderated by an inclusive education environment.

Table 11. Relationship Between Faculty Support and Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City when Moderated by Inclusive Education Environment

Faculty Support	r-value	p-value	Decision
Accessibility	0.544*	0.000	Reject H0
Empathy and Understanding	0.742*	0.000	Reject H0
Mentorship	-0.023	0.101	Accept H0
Collaboration and Teamwork	0.036	0.089	Accept H0
Overall Faculty Support	0.848*	0.000	Reject H0

***Significant @ $p \leq 0.05$**

Legend:

Perfect Correlation for $r=1.00$;
 Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r \leq 1.00$;
 Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r \leq 0.7$;
 Weak Correlation for $0.3 \leq r \leq 0.00$;
 No Correlation for $r=0.00$

This shows the importance of inclusive education in promoting collaboration and communication among faculty members. In an inclusive education environment, teachers recognize the necessity of working together to develop and implement effective teaching strategies that cater to the diverse needs of students with varying abilities, backgrounds, and learning styles. This supports the idea of Mudassir and Norsuhaily (2015) that inclusive education fosters a collaborative and communicative environment among faculty members. Teachers may need to work

closely together to develop and implement inclusive teaching strategies that meet the diverse needs of all students. This collaboration can increase faculty support as educators share resources, ideas, and strategies to enhance pedagogical practices. According to Ezike (2018) found tht inclusive education, which welcomes students with diverse backgrounds, abilities, and needs into the regular classroom, presents teachers with unique challenges and opportunities that can profoundly affect their pedagogical practices and professional growth.

3.2.7. *Moderating Effect of Inclusive Education Environment on the Interaction Between Faculty Support and Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City*—The moderating effect of inclusive education environment (IEE) on the interaction between faculty support (FS) and pedagogical accomplishment (PA) of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City, was tested using regression analysis. Results in Table 12 show that the Beta coefficients for the Step 1 analysis of faculty support (FS) and pedagogical accomplishment (PA) of teachers were = 0.112, S.E. = 0.055, $p \leq 0.05$; and inclusive education environment (IEE) and pedagogical accomplishment (PA) of teachers were = 0.209, S.E.=0.051, $p \leq 0.05$. When faculty support (FS) and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers (PA) were included as the only independent variables (without including an interaction term),

the regression model explained 63.80%. Moreover, Beta coefficients for the Step 2 analysis of faculty support (FS) and pedagogical accomplishment (PA) of teachers were = 0.380, S.E. = .040, $p \leq 0.05$; inclusive education environment (IEE) and pedagogical accomplishment (PA) of teachers were = 0.180, S.E. = 0.044, $p \leq 0.05$; and moderator (FS*IEE) and pedagogical accomplishment (PA) of teachers were = 0.231, S.E.= 0.056, $p \leq 0.05$. Also, it was indicated that when an interaction between faculty support (FS) and inclusive education environment (IEE) was added, the percentage of variance in pedagogical accomplishment (PA) of teachers was 67.90 percent ($R^2 = 0.679$; $p \leq 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values.

Table 12. Moderating Effect of Inclusive Education Environment on the Interaction Between Faculty Support and Pedagogical Accomplishment of Teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City

Step 1	Pedagogical Accomplishment (PA)				
	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decisions
Faculty Support (FS)	.112**	.132	.055	.000	Reject H0
Inclusive Education Environment (IEE)	.209**	.077	.051	.000	Reject H0
$R^2 = 0.444$, F-value = 103.564**, p-value = 0.000					
Step 2					
Faculty Support (FS)	.380**	.577	.040	.000	Reject H0
Inclusive Education Environment (IEE)	.180**	.123	.044	.001	Reject H0
Moderator (FS*IEE)	.231**	.088	.056	.000	Reject H0
$R^2 = 0.679$, F-value = 127.118**, p-value = 0.000					
*Significant @ $p \leq 0.05$					

Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 23.50 percent of the variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.235$). Based on the result, the null hypothesis was rejected as inclusive education environment (IEE) had significantly moderated the relationship between faculty support (FS) and pedagogical accomplishment (PA) of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City. An essential aspect of this endeavor is to ascertain whether the theories that underpin this study have received validation from the findings. As regards to Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura (1986), the result supports the idea that in an inclusive education environment, teachers have the opportunity to observe and learn from each other's inclusive

teaching practices. Faculty members who effectively implement inclusive strategies serve as models for their colleagues, demonstrating how to adapt teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of students. Observing successful inclusive practices can inspire other teachers to adopt similar approaches, leading to increased pedagogical accomplishment. Moreover, the result supports the proposition of Gilavand (2015) which highlights the transformative impact of inclusive education on teacher awareness and empathy within the educational environment. In an inclusive classroom, teachers are confronted with a diverse range of students, each with unique backgrounds, abilities, and learning needs.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the moderating effect of an inclusive education environment on the interaction between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment of teachers utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 178 elementary school teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Faculty support in Digos Oriental District, Digos City, acquired a moderately extensive rating. Faculty support in terms of mentorship, collaboration, and teamwork was rated as moderately extensive, while faculty support in terms of accessibility, empathy, and understanding

was rated as extensive. Pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City was rated as moderately extensive. The pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in terms of content knowledge assessment and feedback use obtained a moderately extensive rating. In contrast, the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in terms of instructional strategies was rated as extensive. Moreover, the inclusive education environment as the moderating variable got a moderately extensive rating. Partial Correlation Analysis indicated that faculty support has a significant positive relationship with the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City when moderated by an inclusive education environment. In addition, faculty support in terms of accessibility, empathy and understanding, mentorship, collaboration, and teamwork have a significant positive relationship with the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos

Oriental District, Digos City, when moderated by an inclusive education environment. The inclusive education environment was a significant moderator of the interaction between faculty support and the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City. When this interaction was added, the percentage variance in the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers increased.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: Faculty support in Digos Oriental District, Digos City, acquired a moderately extensive rating, suggesting that the support, guidance, and resources offered by academic staff or faculty members to students, colleagues, or other educational community members are frequently observed. This was consistent with Ellinger's (2016) idea that faculty support was pivotal in nurturing a positive and inclusive educational setting. When faculty exhibit approachability, empathy, and supportiveness, students feel comfortable seeking help and expressing their opinions, thereby fostering a collaborative and transparent classroom atmosphere. The pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City, was rated as moderately extensive, indicating that the effectiveness and quality of an educator's instructional practices and their ability to facilitate student learning and achievement was sometimes manifested among teachers. This supports Schaufeli and Salanova's (2011) view that pedagogical accomplishment constructs reflect the feelings of energy that lead the teacher to act in an energetic fashion. When teachers feel energized and enthusiastic about their work, they were more likely to exhibit proactive and dynamic behaviors in the classroom. The inclusive education environment in Digos Oriental District, Digos City, was rated as moderately extensive, indicating that the effectiveness and quality of an educator's instructional practices and their ability to facilitate student learning and achievement

is sometimes manifested among teachers. This supports Schaufeli and Salanova's (2011) view that pedagogical accomplishment constructs reflect the feelings of energy that lead the teacher to act in an energetic fashion. When teachers feel energized and enthusiastic about their work, they are more likely to exhibit proactive and dynamic behaviors in the classroom. Faculty support has a significant positive relationship with the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City when moderated by an inclusive education environment. This corresponds with the concept proposed by Mudassir and Norsuhaily (2015) that inclusive education cultivates a collaborative and communicative atmosphere among faculty members. In an inclusive education setting, educators often find themselves collaborating closely to devise and execute teaching strategies that accommodate the varied needs of every student. An inclusive education environment significantly moderates the interaction between faculty support and the pedagogical accomplishment of teachers in Digos Oriental District, Digos City. This aligns with Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986), which suggests that in an inclusive education setting, teachers could observe and gain insights from each other's inclusive teaching approaches. Educators who successfully integrate inclusive strategies serve as role models for their peers, showcasing how to modify teaching techniques to accommodate the diverse requirements of students.

4.3. Recommendations—Department of Education (DepEd) may advocate for inclusive education policies that prioritize the creation of supportive and inclusive learning environments. DepEd should spearhead the development of policies that explicitly promote inclusive education practices across all levels of the education system. These policies should outline clear guidelines and standards for creating inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students, including those with disabili-

ties, special needs, or from marginalized backgrounds. School heads may foster a school culture that values collaboration, empathy, and inclusivity among faculty members. They should lead by example and demonstrate behaviors that reflect these values. By modeling these values in their interactions with faculty members, students, and other stakeholders, school leaders set the tone for the entire school community. Teachers may embrace a growth mindset and be open to learning from colleagues, students, and professional development opportunities to continuously improve their teaching practices. Teachers should engage in reflective practice, regularly reflecting on their teaching methods, student out-

comes, and areas for improvement. By critically examining their practice, teachers can identify strengths and weaknesses and develop strategies for growth. Future researchers may investigate the specific mechanisms through which inclusive education environments moderate the relationship between faculty support and pedagogical accomplishment. Researchers may identify the key variables involved in inclusive education environments, faculty support, and pedagogical accomplishment. This may include factors such as teacher-student relationships, school climate, professional development opportunities, and the availability of resources for inclusive practices.

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